

REACTIVE BLENDING OF POLYETHYLENE AND POLY(L-LACTIC ACID) USING A HIGH-SHEAR EXTRUDER

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1 Introduction

In recent years, environment-friendly polymers have gathered much attention more than ever because of the environmental and energy problems on a global scale. Poly (L-lactic acid) (PLLA) is the most commercial environment-friendly polymer and some industrial plants for producing PLLA in large volume have been established. PLLA is derived from plants which are renewable resources and is biodegradable. Besides, on account of its carbon neutrality, PLLA have a potential to resolve the current problems concerning the global warming. In spite of the environmental friendliness, its brittleness and low heat distortion temperature limit the application of neat PLLA. To overcome these weak points and employ PLLA in wider range of application, extensive works have been carried on PLLA blends with other polymers. Polymer blending is a general method to modify the property of polymers. However, in the case of an immiscible blend, the property of the blend could get worse than that of the original components due to the poor morphology and poor interfacial adhesion between blend components. In such a case, a compatibilizer such as a graft or block copolymer has been used for the blend preparation. Previous works [1–14] reported that the morphology and mechanical performance of the immiscible PLLA blends could be improved by the use of a compatibilizer. These compatibilized PLLA blends sacrifice biodegradability owing to the addition of other polymers and compatibilizers into PLLA. Nevertheless, the blends might reduce the amount of CO₂ emitted over the business life-cycle and thus still have an advantage for the environmental problem.

Among polymers for practical use, low-density polyethylene (LDPE) can be a good opponent party of the PLLA blend since LDPE is the commercially relevant and heavily-used polymers. The realization

of the blend will provide us a new economical and environment-friendly polymer material. Hillmyer et al. [9–11] prepared PLLA/LDPE blends with polyethylene-poly (L-lactic acid) block copolymer as a compatibilizer. These authors demonstrated that the addition of the compatibilizer could improve the miscibility and mechanical properties of the blend. Subsequently, other works reported PLLA/LDPE blends with a compatibilizer such as ethylene glycidyl methacrylate (EGMA) [12], glycidyl methacrylate-grafted poly (ethylene-octene) copolymer [13], grafted low-density polyethylene maleic anhydride [14]. These works clearly exhibited that the use of a compatibilizer was essential to manufacture a practicable LDPE/PLLA blend. Complying with these results, we investigated LDPE/PLLA blends with EGMA as a compatibilizer in the present work. For the fabrication, we employed the high-shear processing which has been established recently by ourselves. The high-shear extruder can reach a maximum rotation speed of 3000 rpm corresponding to a shear rate of about 4400 sec⁻¹. Previous works proved that this is a powerful tool for decreasing the phase size significantly for the immiscible polymer blends [15–17]. Accordingly, we can expect that the high-shear processing will further enhance the properties of the LDPE/PLLA blend.

This work focuses on the blend with the weight ratio of LDPE/PLLA=75/25 as a representative of LDPE-rich blends and is intended as the starting point of investigation of LDPE/PLLA blends in an entire mixing ratio. Our present aim is to estimate the influence of the shear condition on the morphology of the LDPE/PLLA blends and to examine how the mechanical property of a flexible LDPE can be improved by the addition of PLLA.

2 Experimental

2.1 Blend preparation

All samples used in this study was commercially available. The LDPE (MIRASON 50) was obtained from Prime Polymer Co. Ltd. with melt-flow index = 1.9 g/10 min. The PLLA (TERRAMAC TP-4000) with the molecular weight of $M_w=170,000$ was obtained from UNITIKA. Co. Ltd.. The sample included 1.2 % of D-lactic acid content. The reactive compatibilizer EGMA (Igeta bond fast 7L) with glycidyl methacrylate content 6 wt% was provided by Sumitomo chemical Co. Ltd. These samples were dried under vacuum at 80 °C for 24 h before use.

The blends were prepared using a high shear extruder (NHSS2-28, NIIGATA MACHINE TECHNO Co. Ltd., Japan). Fig. 1 is the schematic diagram of the screw and the polymer melt flow route. This screw has a flow hole inside to expert a simultaneous shear and an extensional flow during melt blending. The L/D ratio of the screw is 1.78. The LDPE/PLLA blends were prepared under the screw rotation speeds of 300, 600, and 900 rpm. The melt compounding was carried out at 200 °C for 1–8 min. The temperature of the sample during mixing was controlled with the variation of less than 10 °C using a water-cooling system. The weight ratio of LDPE/PLLA was fixed at 75/25. Concentration of EGMA is 5 wt% with respect to the whole weight fraction of LDPE/PLLA. After blending, the samples were hot-pressed at 200 °C to form a sheet of 1 mm thickness under the pressure of 10 MPa for 5 min, followed by quenching with circulating water.

2.2 Characterization

Morphology of the blends was observed by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). A Philips XL-20 SEM was used for SEM observations at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. The samples were fractured after immersion in liquid nitrogen for 10 min. The fracture surface was then coated with a thin layer of gold. TEM observations were carried out using a JEM 1230 (JEOL Ltd.) at an acceleration voltage of 120 kV. The blend samples were ultramicrotomed at –120 °C to a section with a thickness of about 70 nm. The sections were then stained with RuO₄ for 20 min.

Dynamical mechanical analysis (DMA) was carried out with a Rheovibron DDV-25FP (Orientec Corp.) in the tensile mode. All the measurements were

performed in the linear region with the strain of 0.03 %. Dynamic loss ($\tan \delta$) was determined at 1 Hz and a heating rate of 3 °C/min as a function of temperature range from –150 °C to 170 °C.

Tensile tests were carried out according to the JIS K7113 test method using dumb-bell-shaped samples punched out from the molded sheets. The tests were performed with Tensilon UMT-300 (Orientec Co. Ltd.) at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min at 20 °C and 50 % relative humidity.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Morphology of the LDPE/PLLA blends

Fig. 2a shows the SEM image of the LDPE/PLLA blend without a compatibilizer prepared at 300 rpm for 2min. PLLA forms domains dispersed in the LDPE matrix. The PLLA domain size ranges from 1 to 10 μm . The adhesion between the two phases is clearly weak. We also examined the morphologies of the blends at 600 and 900 rpm, which are not given here for the sake of simplicity. It was found that there was no clear improvement at a higher screw rotation speed. Thus, the morphology was independent of the screw rotation speed for the blends without a compatibilizer.

Fig. 2b shows the SEM image of the LDPE/PLLA blend with EGMA content 5 wt% prepared at 300 rpm for 2 min. The image indicates that the addition of the compatibilizer dramatically reduce the average size of the PLLA domain down to about 1.5 μm . Kim et al. [12] reported the PLLA/LDPE=20/80 blends with EGMA. They demonstrated that the epoxide groups of EGMA could react either with –COOH or with –OH of the PLLA end groups to form a grafting copolymer that could function as a compatibilizer. The presence of the compatibilizer could improve the morphology of the immiscible blend. However, the elongation at break of the blends was quite low compared with LDPE.

Subsequently, we performed SEM observations on the blends with EGMA prepared at 600 and 900 rpm for 2min, as demonstrated in Figs. 2c and 2d. The morphologies change dramatically compared with that of 300 rpm. As shown in Fig. 2b, the clear white PLLA domain in the LDPE matrix is observed for 300 rpm. In the case of 600 and 900 rpm, the relatively dark phase appears in the LDPE matrix

and the interface between these phases is not well defined. The change in the appearance clearly indicates that the high-shear processing improves the blend morphology. The average size of the dark phase for 600 rpm is less than 1 μm . Compared with 600 rpm, the blend prepared at 900 rpm shows a wider distribution of the dark domain size less than 4 μm .

As discussed above, the shear condition has an influence on the morphology of the LDPE/PLLA/EGMA blends when the mixing time is fixed at 2 min. We then examined the mixing time dependence on the morphology. Firstly, SEM observations were performed on the LDPE/PLLA/EGMA blends prepared at 600 rpm for 1 and 4 min as shown in Figs. 3a and 3b, respectively. In the SEM image for 1 min, the white PLLA domain is observed like the blend prepared at 300 rpm for 2 min (Fig. 2b), implying that the mixing time of 1 min at 600 rpm is insufficient to attain the improved morphology. Fig. 3b indicates that the blend morphology for 4 min is as almost same as that for 2 min (Fig. 2c) except for the slight increase of the average dark domain size. Secondary, as shown in Fig. 3c, the morphology of the blend at 900 rpm for 1 min was observed for the comparison with that for 2 min (Fig. 2d). The morphology for 1 min is seen to have a fine morphology as is the case for 2 min. Thus, the time required for the improvement of the morphology much depends on the screw rotation speed. In our study, we could obtain the fine morphology for 1 min by the application of 900 rpm.

In order to reveal the mechanism of the change in the blend morphology depending on the screw rotation speed, we performed TEM observations on some blends. Fig. 4a shows the TEM image of the LDPE/PLLA/EGMA blend prepared at 300 rpm for 2 min. In the image, EGMA is observed as the dark particles in the PLLA phase because EGMA is more readily stained than PLLA by RuO_4 . EGMA forms small particles with the particle size less than 0.2 μm and dispersed discretely in the PLLA phase. This result indicates that EGMA has the higher affinity with PLLA rather than LDPE. Figs. 4b and 4c show the TEM image of the blends at 600 rpm for 4 min and at 900 rpm for 1 min, as representatives of the blends which have improved morphologies. In these

cases, EGMA locates at the interface between LDPE and PLLA phases, leading to the good adhesion at the interface. These TEM observations clarify that the high-shear processing can form the grafted structure via EGMA between LDPE and PLLA phases. As a result, EGMA becomes to act as a compatibilizer more effectively.

3.2 Mechanical properties of LDPE/PLLA blends

Tensile stress-strain curves of LDPE and some blends are shown in Fig. 5. The main tensile properties such as tensile strength and elongation at break determined from these curves are presented in Table 1. LDPE is very flexible and shows a high value of elongation at break ($> 750\%$), but the tensile strength is low. The blends without EGMA show the high tensile strength, but breaks at the low elongation at break due to the poor morphology. The addition of EGMA improves tensile properties, yielding the increase of the elongation at break up to 96.7 % at 300 rpm. Furthermore, the blends prepared under the high-shear conditions of 600 and 900 rpm show a considerable increase in the elongation at break up to about 330 %. Compared with the blend under the low-shear condition of 300 rpm, the values of the tensile strength are also increased for 600 and 900 rpm. Table 1 also shows the values of storage modulus estimated from the DMA analysis. The storage modulus of the blends with EGMA is as almost same as that of the blends without EGMA. From the result of the mechanical measurements, it is found that LDPE/PLLA blends which have fine morphologies show the relative high modulus and high stiffness compared to LDPE, keeping a sufficient elongation character.

4 Conclusions

The morphology of the LDPE /PLLA blends without EGMA has a bigger PLLA domain in the LDPE matrix and weak interface. Those blends exhibit poor mechanical properties. It is found that EGMA is an effective reactive compatibilizer for the LDPE/PLLA blend as indicated by the significant decrease of the PLLA domain size. Moreover, the application of the high-shear conditions positively affected the morphology of the blend system. The blends obtained by the combination of reactive blending and high-shear processing exhibited an excellent improvement in the mechanical properties.

In the present work, we succeeded in fabricating the environment-friendly LDPE/PLLA blends which have excellent mechanical properties. It is expected that LDPE can be derived from plants as well as PLLA in near future. Then, LDPE/PLLA blends will further contribute to the settlement of the environmental and energy problems, especially the reduced dependence on petroleum resources.

Fig.1. Full-automatic high-shear extruder and the schematic diagram for the screw used in the high-shear extruder and the flow route of polymer melt during mixing.

Fig.2. SEM image of LDPE/PLLA=75/25 blend prepared at 600 rpm for 2min (a), and LDPE/PLLA/EGMA=75/25/5 blend prepared at 300 (b), 600 (c) and 900 rpm (d) for 2 min.

Fig.3. SEM image of LDPE/PLLA/EGMA=75/25/5 blend at 600 rpm for 1 min (a) and 4min (b), and at 900 rpm for 1 min (c).

Fig.4. TEM image of LDPE/PLLA/EGMA=75/25/5 prepared at 300 (a) and 600 rpm (b) for 2 min, and at 900 rpm for 1 min (c).

Fig.5. Tensile strain-stress curves for LDPE (a), LDPE/PLLA=75/25 blend prepared at 300 rpm for 2 min (b), and LDPE/PLLA/EGMA=75/25/5 blends at 300 (c), 600 (d), and 900 rpm (e) for 2 min.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of neat LDPE and LEPE/PLLA blends.

Samples	Storage modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
LDPE	314.3	9.2	771.6
LDPE/PLLA 300 rpm	442.3	12.8	43.1
LDPE/PLLA/EGMA 300 rpm	442.2	10.2	96.7
LDPE/PLLA/EGMA 600 rpm	445.5	11.5	327.5
LDPE/PLLA/EGMA 900 rpm	443.8	11.6	329.5

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